

Supplementary Materials

Table S1. Valid insect source areas of *L. sticticalis* in northern China in recent years.

Province	City	Source
Inner Mongolia	Bayannur City	2022 Survey Data
	Ordos City	2022 Survey Data
	Ulanqab City	2022 Survey Data
	Chifeng City	Zhang, Y., et al., 2022 [60]
	Hinggan League	Zhang, Y., et al., 2022 [60]
	Xilingol League	Chen, Z.Y., et al. 2022 [12]
	Baotou City	Chen, Z.Y., 2022 [14]
	Tongliao City	Chen, Z.Y., 2022 [14]
	Hulun Buir	2024 Survey Data
Hebei	Zhangjiakou City	2022 Survey Data
	Chengde City	2022 Survey Data
Beijing	Beijing City	2022 Survey Data
Jilin	Songyuan City	Zhang, Y., et al., 2022 [60]
	Baicheng City	Chen, Z.Y., 2022 [14]
	Jilin City	2023 Survey Data
Liaoning	Chaoyang City	2022 Survey Data
Heilongjiang	Harbin City	2023 Survey Data
Shanxi	Xinzhou City	2022 Survey Data
	Datong City	Zhang, Y., et al., 2022 [60]
	Shuozhou City	Zeng, J., et al., 2014 [54]
Shaanxi	Yulin City	Zhang, Y., et al., 2022 [60]
Ningxia	Shizuishan City	Zhang, Y., et al., 2022 [60]
Xinjiang	Altay Prefecture	2023 Survey Data